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IMPROVEMENT OF SINGLE-PHASE POWER FACTOR CORRECTION CIRCUITS USING SAMPLE-AND-HOLD TECHNIQUES

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Abstract. This paper describes improvement of single-phase PFC circuits made by using sample and hold technique in order to achieve minimum low harmonic content of the input current. Theoretical foundations are described and used to achieve a successful implementation. Guidelines for designing the regulator are presented. Experimental converter is built and tested. The results show that almost ideal THD is achieved (with high frequency content ignored) using novel technique with extremely high bandwidth.

Keywords: Power factor correction, Single-phase systems, Total harmonic distortion, Zero-order sample and hold, PI regulator.

1. INTRODUCTION

Single-phase power factor correction (PFC) circuits are commonly used as an interface between low power loads (up to 3kW) and utility line [1]. In the power level higher than 500W, it is a common practice to use a boost-type PFC rectifier, shown in Fig. 1. Continuous conduction mode is more desirable because of the smaller high frequency content. Consequently, the input filter becomes smaller in size and cost.

Fig. 1. Boost-type PFC rectifier

Regulation of this circuit involves two control loops: voltage and current loop. The voltage loop (the outer one) senses the output voltage error signal and processes it to the voltage regulator. The voltage regulator output is the reference signal for the control of the input current amplitude V_c . The current loop (the inner one) multiplies the amplitude reference by the rectified sinewave, generating the inductor current reference value. Then, one of the conventional current-programming techniques is used to control the inductor current.

Assuming proper current-regulator operation, the input current follows the sinusoidal shape of the input voltage. As a consequence, the output voltage consists of a DC value and a superimposed second harmonic waveform (twice the line frequency) [2]. This second harmonic waveform is processed through the voltage regulator, resulting in

distortion of regulator output (the amplitude reference distortion). Since the input current amplitude is distorted, then the input current deviates from sinewave.

Conventional solution is to implement a PI regulator with sufficient second harmonic attenuation [3]. This directly influences the dynamics of the converter, slowing down the response on fast changes. On the other hand, if good dynamic response is required, then PI regulator will distort the input current with high degree and much larger input filter is necessary.

The purpose of this paper is to present the technique to retain the fast dynamic response with excellent input current THD. In section 2, the basic principles are presented. Section 3 gives the design guidelines, while the section 4 presents experimental results. This novel technique is compared to the conventional method with a summary presented in section 5.

2. BASIC PRINCIPLES

Spectral analysis of the output voltage clearly shows that the second harmonic is the dominant unwanted harmonic (neglecting switching ripple). This voltage harmonic must be filtered out if fast regulation is required. In simple words, any spectral component close to 100Hz would be covered by 100Hz ripple. A high order notch filter can be implemented, but it increases the circuit complexity and the cost.

One unconventional approach is to use the zero-order sample-and-hold circuit [4]. Fig. 2. shows its amplitude frequency characteristic relative to the sampling frequency f_s . It is quite clear that at frequencies $n:f_s$ ($n=1,2,\dots$) the attenuation is infinitely large (gain equal to zero). Aliasing does occur, but choosing the appropriate sampling instants will compensate the effects. Therefore, inserting this S&H circuit within the regulation loop completely cancels the

influence of output second harmonic on the input current distortion.

Fig. 2. Amplitude characteristic of zero-order S&H circuit

The following step is to determine the most convenient position for inserting. Fig. 3. shows a block-diagram of conventional voltage-loop. $G_{ps}(s)$ is a transfer function of the power stage together with the current-loop closed. The input to this block is V_c , the reference value of input current amplitude. $G_r(s)$ is a voltage regulator transfer function, usually of PI type. Its input is the output voltage error signal. According to Fig. 3., there are three possible positions for inserting the S&H circuit. These positions are marked with small crosses and numbered by 1,2 and 3.

Fig. 3. Block-diagram of conventional voltage regulation

Each position has its own features:

Position 1: the signal is unipolar, with very high magnitude (typically 400V). A voltage divider with gain K_v must be used to scale it down to a level which S&H circuit can accept. Power supply can be unipolar.

Aliasing does occur, and the second harmonic transfers into a DC signal, which is superimposed to the average output voltage value. If it is to be avoided, the sampling instants must occur when the second harmonic is equal to zero. It is shown in Appendix A that these instants are very close to the input AC voltage zero-crossings. Consequently, zero-crossing detector connected to the PFC circuit's input terminals generate the command signal for the S&H circuit, and the sampled value is free from second harmonic. Regulator that includes the S&H circuit in the position 1, we will call regulator type 1 in the rest of the paper.

Position 2: sampling the error signal shows the same features considering aliasing as sampling the output voltage,

since the reference value is constant. However, the error signal is of bipolar nature and bipolar power supply is required. It is a good technical reason to discard this solution and it won't be considered any more in the rest of the paper.

Position 3: the signal here contains the DC value and a certain amount of second harmonic. Therefore, unipolar power supply is sufficient. However, this harmonic content is phase-shifted from its original, and sampling cause aliasing which can not be easily compensated. Two approaches are possible: either the line zero-crossing detector signal will be delayed by the certain angle, or it will be used undelayed. If undelayed, there will be aliasing in the amplitude reference, but the integral action of the regulator will set the zero-error steady state. Regulator that includes the S&H circuit in the position 3 we will call regulator type 2 in the rest of the circuit.

3. CHOOSING REGULATOR PARAMETERS

PI regulator is necessary to achieve regulation without static error [5]. Classical continuous-time feedback techniques can be used to choose the parameters for three regulators: conventional, regulator type 1 and regulator type 2. The only uncertainty is due to the nonlinear nature of S&H circuit. It can be overcome using modified Padé approximation, already used in current-mode analysis [6]. A linear, second-order transfer function is obtained which represent the S&H circuit very good up to the half of the sampling frequency. A review of transfer functions is summarized in Tab. 1., for the case of resistive load.

block name	transfer function
power stage together with current-loop	$G_{ps}(s) = \frac{\eta \cdot V_m}{2CV_{out}R_s} \cdot \frac{1}{s + \frac{2}{RC}}$
PI regulator	$G_r(s) = K_i + \frac{1}{sT_i}$
zero-order S&H circuit	$G_{sh}(s) \approx \frac{\omega_n^2}{s^2 + \frac{\omega_n\pi}{2}s + \omega_n^2}, \omega_n = \pi \cdot f_s$

Tab. 1. Review of transfer functions

where:

V_m is the input voltage amplitude,
 V_c is the reference of the input current amplitude,
 V_{out} is the average output voltage value,
 η is the converter efficiency,
 R_i is the transfer ratio of current sensor,
 C is the output capacitance value,
 R is the load resistance,
 f_s is the sampling frequency.

In order to determine the parameters, it is requested that open-loop crossover frequency equals 18Hz with phase

margin of 45° . The crossover frequency is higher than usual (10-12 Hz), but it assures higher bandwidth. Since the lightest load is the most critical case regarding stability, choosing the parameters will be done for that case.

Experimental single phase PFC-boost converter was built with the following parameters:

line voltage $V_{in}=110V/50Hz$,
 output voltage $V_{out}=220V$,
 nominal power $P_{out}=750W$ ($R=63\Omega$),
 inductance $L=2mH$,
 capacitance $C=1000\mu F$,
 switching frequency $f_{sw}=5kHz$,
 Minimum load $P_{min}=340W$ ($R=143\Omega$).

Also, it is assumed that with the lightest load, the efficiency is around $\eta=70\%$.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In order to confirm the theoretical predictions, two subjects must be examined: the input current waveform distortion and the output voltage response to the sudden load change, from maximum to minimum and vice versa.

According to section 3, the following regulator parameters were chosen for three regulators:

conventional: $K_f=0.3$, $T_f=22ms$
 regulator 1: $K_f=1/44$, $K_i=21.6$, $T_f=1.2ms$.
 regulator 2: $K_f=0.5$, $T_f=50ms$

Steady state analysis

Conventional regulator: Fig. 4. shows the voltage regulator output and the inductor current reference value. A high intensity second harmonic is present in the regulator output. When it is multiplied by the rectified unity-sinewave, the inductor current reference value is distorted, and also the converter input current (Fig. 5.).

Regulator type 1: Sampling the scaled output voltage at 100Hz rate completely rejects the second harmonic, as shown in Fig. 6. Therefore, the regulator input is a constant value, and so is its output. Consequently, the input current is undistorted (Fig. 7.).

Regulator type 2: Although the voltage regulator output contains the second harmonic waveform, it is sampled at 100Hz rate, giving the constant input current amplitude. Consequently, the inductor current reference is undistorted and so is the input current (Fig. 8.).

Harmonic distortion

Spectral contents of input currents are analysed, and the normalised results together with the THD are shown in Tab. 2. Switching ripple wasn't taken into account.

Fig. 4. The steady-state voltage regulator output and inductor current reference value in case of conventional regulator

Fig. 5. Input current waveform in case of conventional regulator

Fig. 6. Output voltage and its sampled value in case of regulator type 1

Fig. 7. Inductor current reference and the circuit input current in case of regulator type 1

Fig. 8. Input current in case of regulator type 2

	conventional regulator	regulator 1	regulator 2
1 st harmonic	1	1	1
3 rd harmonic	0.060	0.0012	0.001
5 th harmonic	0.013	0.0009	0.0009
7 th harmonic	0.008	0.0006	0.0008
9 th harmonic	0.004	0.0005	0.0005
THD [%]	6.25	0.17	0.16

Tab. 2. the input currents spectral content

Obviously, a great improvement is achieved only by addition of a simple hardware.

Dynamic features

The testing sequence was to expose the converter to sudden load change from maximum to minimum, than back to maximum again and so on. Two signals were observed and

recorded: the output voltage and the reference of input current amplitude. These are shown in Figs. 9., 10 and 11 for the conventional, regulator type 1 and regulator type 2, respectively. The settling time is almost the same, due to the same criterion used when choosing the parameters.

Fig. 9. Output voltage (upper trace) and the reference of the input current amplitude (lower trace) in case of conventional regulator

Fig. 10. Output voltage (upper trace) and the reference of the input current amplitude (lower trace) in case of regulator type 1

Fig. 11. Output voltage (upper trace) and the reference of the input current amplitude (lower trace) in case of regulator type 2

5. DISCUSSION

The experiment has shown that it is possible to have good input current THD and fast response of the output simultaneously. The conventional method can achieve the fast response but at the price of high current THD. Two novel control methods enable very high bandwidth, which can be made as high as 25Hz (half the line frequency). It is twice the conventional result.

What can also be seen from the experiment is that the conventional regulator has two limiting factors:

a) the regulator output second harmonic must not exceed the DC value,

b) the regulator output second harmonic must not distort the input current excessively.

The latter limit is more important, and it is used when designing the practical regulator.

With regulator 2, the requirement b) is already met. Only one limiting factor remains, which effectively lowers the bandwidth (below 25Hz).

With regulator 1, both requirements are met, so this method can achieve its full potential. Additionally, the S&H circuit can be inserted between the scaled output voltage and any of the commercial integrated PFC regulator chips. This way, the simple hardware can be used to improve the regulation significantly.

6. CONCLUSION

Two novel control methods are presented to improve the single-phase PFC-circuit performances. Both are based on employing the zero-order S&H circuit within the voltage regulation loop. It is shown that 100Hz output voltage ripple effect on the current-shape and the dynamics can be rejected. The design guidelines are given, and the experiment is performed which confirms the superiority of novel methods over the conventional.

With this modification, PFC regulation becomes less sensitive to the output voltage ripple. It leads to an idea that the expensive overdimensioned output capacitor can be decreased without effect on the input current shape, while the dynamics will be improved because of the lowered system inertia. It is a subject of further investigation, and the results will be certainly reported in a short time.

7. REFERENCES

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6. APPENDIX A

Let the converter is ideal, meaning that low frequency content is processed without losses. Then, the instantaneous input power is:

$$p_{in}(t) = V_m \sin(\omega t) \cdot I_m \sin(\omega t) \quad (A.1)$$

$$p_{in}(t) = \frac{V_m I_m}{2} [1 - \cos(2\omega t)] = P_{DC} - p_2(t)$$

The DC power (average value) is transferred to the load, while the second harmonic power $p_2(t)$ is transferred to the capacitor. It is true, because at this frequency, the capacitor is much smaller impedance than the load is. Then:

$$\frac{V_m I_m}{2} \cos(2\omega t) = p_2(t) = u_{C2}(t) \cdot (C \cdot \frac{du_{C2}(t)}{dt}) \quad (A.2)$$

where $u_{C2}(t)$ is the output voltage second harmonic component. The solution has the form:

$$u_{C2}^2(t) = \frac{V_m I_m}{2\omega C} \sin(\omega t) + c_1, \quad (A.3)$$

where c_1 is the constant of integration and it is equal to zero, otherwise there would be a DC value, which is opposite to AC nature of u_{C2} .

It is clear that at the time instants $t=k\pi/T$ ($k=0,1,2,\dots$) the second harmonic is zero, exactly when the input voltage has zero-crossings. In reality, the load impedance adds some phase delay, which can be neglected in most cases.

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